

Semantically-driven Interpretation of Stakeholder Requirements and Quantification of Impact to Layout Design

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Abstract. Requirements elucidation is a significant part of early-stage ship design, especially in naval architecture for complex ships. During a vessel's acquisition process, the stakeholders propose requirements in statements, regulations, Concepts of Operations (CONOPS), vignettes, and Minutes of Meetings, all expressed in natural language. However, bridging these natural language requirements and their impact on the final design remains an open research problem. This research proposes a framework that utilizes semantics interpretation to map the natural language requirements (R) to the layers of the systems architecture: Functional (F), Logical (L), and Physical (P). This paper proposes to use semantics to better understand the effect of requirements on design change occurring in the logical and physical architecture layers of the system architecture. This research also introduces the classification of the requirements on a two-dimensional axis system, with one axis being their importance to the stakeholders and the other axis evaluating their elasticity (i.e., if they can be interpreted in more than one way). This classification provides insights into the characteristics of requirements that may impact the physical design. The proposed framework shows potential for identifying and tracing the propagation of changes and uncertainties stemming from the requirements to the other layers of the systems architecture. This paper showcases the framework through a case study on the semantic interpretation of redundancy and safety regulations for the design of a short-sea vessel's engine room. The results show that "hard" and "elastic" safety requirements are more influential on the layout arrangement and thus the shape of the generated design space.

Key words: ship design, model based systems engineering, systems architecture, semantic knowledge models, regulations

1. Introduction

Early-Stage Ship Design (ESSD) refers to the iterative process that produces a ship able to complete specific missions and adhere to set requirements as dictated by stakeholders, i.e., shipowners, classification societies, while remaining technically, economically, and environmentally feasible [1, 2, 3]. This process is characterized as a multidisciplinary, highly complex endeavor involving stakeholders with often-times conflicting requirements. This endeavor starts with the ESSD and specifically the requirements elucidation phase, that relies heavily on articulating and interpreting the verbal, written, or implied requirements such as regulations (both from classification societies and flag states), Concept of Operations (CONOPS), vignettes, or Minutes of Meeting [4]. However, as discussed by Arrigan et al.,[5], this process creates a "universe of discourse", an area of misalignment between what is expressed by the language and the understanding of reality, which the naval architect has to navigate through. The naval architect is a critical part of the design process, as both the interpreter of the requirements set by the stakeholders, as well as the one making the design choices [6]. The naval architect needs to produce designs compliant with additional safety and redundancy regulations to store and handle alternative fuels [7, 8]; while technologies alternative to internal combustion engine (ICE), like Fuel Cell (FC) or batteries impose additional integration requirements, adding to complexity of alternative design pathways evaluation [7]. Consequently, the task of designing cleaner vessels using alternative fuels introduces overlooked design challenges linked to the verbal statements.

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1.1. Interpretation of Stakeholder Requirements

The requirements elucidation phase in ESSD is faced with numerous challenges, with these often being more prominent in military projects[9] due to the multiple budget restrictions that apply. However, even with a more structured process, the success of a navy ship's design is not guaranteed, particularly in terms of its operational effectiveness. This can lead to overspending and a derailed schedule. The Littoral Combat Ship (LCS) class from the US Navy [10, 11] is a prime example of this failure to meet the desired performance level. According to [5, 12, 13, 14], the LCS class vessels' failure can be traced back to the requirements elucidation phase. One of the many challenges the designers of the LCSs encountered was the requirement for a speed of 40 knots. This requirement was set during the ESSD, with little understanding of either its genesis or its impact on the vessel and its ability to perform the required functions [15].

This challenge of requirements elucidation, described in the literature [9] by the lack of understanding of the impact of the requirements and regulations on physical and logical aspects of the vessel's Systems Architecture (SA)[16], is encountered throughout the naval architecture community. This phase is intertwined with the concept exploration phase [17]. Recently introduced methods, like concurrent design and Model-Based Systems Engineering (MBSE), are attempting to facilitate the dialogue between stakeholders and to create traceability between the requirements and the other layers of the SA [18, 19, 20]. However, these methods rely on human interpretation of both the stakeholder requirements to generate the dependencies between the components of the SA. MBSE has been used to observe the interactions between the components of the SA and create a traceability chain to observe the impact of a component. Kooij,[21] demonstrated a method to track the dependencies and interaction among different levels of requirements using Capella for a Patrol Vessel.

1.2. Quantification of Requirement Impact to Layout Design

To date, the process of requirements elucidation and the quantification of requirements impact on the physical design of a vessel have remained unlinked[5, 9]. Although Arrigan et al.,[5] highlighted that failing to interpret the linguistic requirements to concrete design requirements has led to unforeseen design failures at an advanced phase of the design process, no method has yet been proposed to quantify the statements impact for the design and identify the qualities of the statements that lead to uncertain design requirements and parameters. Souflis-Rigas et al.,[7] highlighted the uncertainty in estimations regarding the size impact for methanol fuel adoption. Typically, methods dealing with uncertainty in ship design are focused on the lifecycle evaluation [22, 23], and the survivability of distributed systems under attack [24], with limited focus on the uncertainty propagation within the design process impacting the actual physical space of the vessel.

Integrating qualitative and quantitative analysis while ensuring traceability poses a significant challenge for design tools. Furthermore, ill-defined regulatory statements grant designers freedom for interpretation, which can lead to uncertainty regarding the inputs required for the definition of a concept [4]. Dowling et al., Habben Jansen et al.,[25, 26] proposed methods to handle this uncertainty when considering dependencies among systems and evaluated the vulnerability of the systems that may be replaced. In Vos et al.,[27], a topology generator for distribution systems is developed, and the complexity of their interdependencies is highlighted. These studies represented the systems and their interdependencies using graphs and limited their analysis to the logical architecture layer. The identified systems interdependencies lacked a connection to the regulations driving them and their impact on the physical integration.

1.3. Research scope and contributions

Building on the uncertainty quantification framework by Souflis-Rigas et al.,[7], this paper investigates how regulations (i.e., related to safety and redundancy) propagate through topology and physical design constraints to impact the actual physical design of an engine room. Previous work from Kougiatsos et al.,[28] examined the interdependencies between systems using unweighted graphs. However, the considered system architectures did not trace back to specific regulations dictating the required dependencies among systems. Additionally,

This paper draws inspiration from the concept introduced by Arrigan et al.,[5] to interpret vessel design requirements as ontologies, and proposes an interpretation of linguistic requirements using semantics to modelling inputs. In addition, the present research highlights the undefined parameters that are either a source of design freedom or design uncertainty. Their potential impact can be quantified using a probabilistic layout modelling tool, previously developed in Souflis-Rigas et al.,[29].

This paper aims to bridge the research gap between qualitative statements and quantitative impact on the physical design of the vessel, to gain a better understanding of when and why problems arise. The main research question is:

How can statements be interpreted to trace the dependencies between systems and regulations to generate the systems' topologies and design conditions, so that the impact of ill-defined regulations on the size and connection of an engine room can be quantified?

To this end, we develop a framework to link the linguistic statements of requirements to their quantitative impact using semantics and a probabilistic layout modelling tool. The proposed contributions are:

1. A framework that utilizes semantics interpretation of natural language statements or requirements (R), according to ISO, to the layers of the systems architecture: Functional (F), Logical (L), and Physical (P) using graphs (Section 3.1.).
2. The use of semantics' classification to position the statements in a two-dimensional axis system to better understand the characteristics of regulations that may result in larger modifications to the physical architecture (Section 3.2.).
3. Scenario-based analysis of the impact of ambiguous regulation statements on the physical architecture of a methanol-fuelled engine room. This aims to quantify the impact of the uncertainty rooted in ambiguous regulations and, using the statement classifications, identify the shortcomings of such regulations (Section 4.).

2. Literature Review

2.1. Ship Design and Requirements elucidation

With the human factor at the core of ship design, several efforts have been made to reduce the ambiguity present in the process and to better organize the interactions among stakeholders [9, 30]. Such a method is the “ontological commitment” concept from Arrigan et al.,[5]. This method proposes identifying a “universe of discourse” and resolving “ontological anchors” to facilitate the discussions and ensure all stakeholders utilize words with the same meaning. Arrigan et al.,[5] states that “the translation of uncertain or ambiguous language into concrete design requirements has been overlooked from a linguistic standpoint”. Further supporting this argument is that ontology in literature in the field of systems engineering usually does not refer to the linguistic or philosophical meaning of the word [31]. Instead, ontology in ship design and systems engineering commonly refers to the structure representing the relationships between the components described in MBSE [32, 33]. Yang et al., Lu et al., Arista et al.,[31, 34, 35] present different structures for the connection between the layers of MBSE. Most notable is the “Graph, Object, Point, Property, Role, and Relationship” (GOPPRRE) ontology by Lu et al.,[34], which is used for the formalization of the Metadata's architecture and the communication between MBSE languages.

The ontological interpretation of stakeholder requirements shows potential in enhancing both vessel design and operation. In recent years, a handful of papers in the literature have tried bridging the available knowledge on vessel requirements with Large Language Models (LLMs). Agyei et al.,[36] focus on safety requirements and design a novel framework that integrates LLM with risk-aware decision-making for autonomous maritime navigation. Pei et al.,[37] explore LLM-assisted vessel guidance and navigation and compare the accuracy of different LLMs on this task. Nonetheless, the requirements in the above works are interpreted in big chunks, leading to high computational load for the models, while the cognitive ability of the models is tested by solely considering multiple-choice tests. Considering functional requirements,Erikstad,[38] use multi-agent LLMs to assist in optimising the vessel system design during ESSD.

In particular, the use of multiple interconnected LLM agents, each focusing on a simpler task of the overall design process, is shown to render more accurate results related to the modelling of the optimisation problem and the obtained design. Despite the computational load of the LLM agents decreasing in this case, the communication requirements between the agents are considerably increased. An alternative solution to this problem would be to simplify the provided information through the use of a suitable qualitative modeling technique. The choice of technique should be made considering the current state of practice in ship design and the bottlenecks encountered in this process.

Traditionally, designers have relied on two-dimensional drawings to outline the geometry and structure of a ship. Still, much of the design rationale could get lost in translation as the project progressed [39, 40]. To keep track of the design choices that affect the outcome, Le Poole,[6] developed a design rationale tool that focused on tracing undocumented design choices to relevant design actions. More specifically, they linked the design decision, i.e., of moving a component or allocating a space to a compartment, to documenting the underlying reasoning resulting in a concept design. This design rationale contained in the regulation can be captured during EESD and preserved throughout the vessel’s development [41]. Semantics have already been successfully used in shipbuilding to unify the concepts within the field [42], in smart building technology [43] to facilitate the reconfigurability of internal temperature control, and in the field of aerial navigation for the reconstruction of missing inspection features [44]. Semantics databases, relying on the input/output description of the systems included in the vessel layout, have been previously used to design constraints [45] and link with the vessel automation systems[28]. However, the impact of functional requirements (i.e., linguistic statements) on vessel topology and layout design has not yet been properly explored.

2.2. Complexity of requirements for methanol integration during EESD

The design task becomes more complex because alternative fuels like methanol, ammonia, and hydrogen introduce additional requirements regarding the fuel handling, safety, and fire protection [7, 46]. Conceptual studies have evaluated the design impact of methanol integration either based on calculating additional volume or displacement to the vessel for additional tanks [47, 48] and accounting for the hazardous areas [8]. However, these studies reached inconsistent results on the size effect, while also overlooking critical aspects like ventilation, safe handling, and existing design requirements that affect the produced design or the various alternative configurations that may exist [7].

Methanol can be integrated in a vessel using FC or hybrid configurations using batteries as well [7, 49]. The classification rules [50] provided specifications for methanol-fuelled prepared ships focused only on dual-fuel engines. Regulatory requirements for configurations integrating FCs and batteries have been overlooked when evaluating the impact of methanol integration. This means that additional regulations or statements that are potentially conflicting need to be processed by the designer. The wide variety of requirements create a complex set of statements and dependencies that the designer needs to process, synthesize and propose solutions. When reflecting on the requirements that are set during EESD, among others, they include the sailing speed, redundancy of the systems configuration (i.e., DP2 or DP3 level), and safety requirements to safely store and handle the fuel [9].

Design studies for methanol-fuelled vessels lack traceability between the regulations that cause a design change (i.e., additional volume or space loss due to methanol safety measures) and the actual design choice being made [7, 47, 48]. The traceability to the source of design change or failure becomes important, as inconsistencies in the size impact of methanol integration have been highlighted [7, 51]. Most studies follow a point-based design approach (i.e., focusing on altering an existing baseline vessel design using diesel to methanol), focusing on limited requirements specific to methanol tanks (i.e., the cofferdams), while numerous safety considerations and systems are necessary [8, 50, 52, 53] to derisk methanol’s hazardous properties.

3. Methods

In this paper, we propose a qualitative method, based on semantics (see [28]), to link the regulatory requirements of vessel design with the resulting logical and physical architecture (see [7]). Semantics can

formalize relationships between systems and their corresponding architecture. To quantitatively assess the impact of different requirements during ESSD, key performance indices (KPI) related to engine room size are applied. This framework is shown in Figure 1., with the main contributions highlighted inside dashed lines, namely the regulations database based on semantic interpretation and the quantification of their impact to the physical design. There are two key entities involved in this process: the stakeholders and the designer. In the context of this paper, stakeholders are responsible for setting the design requirements. On the other hand, the designer interprets the statements in order to generate inputs for the layout tool. The designer also evaluates the results' implications. This framework allows for the analysis of the underlying ontology in qualitative statements (i.e. regulations) and the quantification of its impact on the physical architecture. It is composed of the following main parts:

Figure 1.: General framework for the semantic interpretation of stakeholder requirements and the quantification of their impact on the design. The different levels of MBSE are indicated. The main contributions of this paper are shown with dashed lines. (\mathcal{F}_r : stakeholder requirements and regulations, \mathcal{F}_s : considered components, \mathcal{F} : semantic database, \mathcal{V} : vertices, \mathcal{E} : edges, \mathcal{C} : constraints, p : probability densities of length and connections cost distributions, U_c : uncertainty in the constraints)

- **Requirements:** The functional requirements of the regulations for the corresponding systems, and the reference size properties of the systems, as logical and physical requirements, are added to the semantics database by the stakeholders and designers, respectively, based on [28]. The semantics interpretation process is explained in more detail in Section 3.3.
- **Logical Architecture:** The logical architecture layer provides the connection between the functional requirements set and the physical architecture. Logical architecture in this paper represents the dependencies among systems (i.e., topology) [54]. Additionally, based on the semantic interpretation of the regulations and specifically the constraint part, the method extracts the ambiguous statements that can serve as uncertainties for the layout tool employed in the physical architecture layer, by identifying the ambiguous constraints of the statements according to ISO, maintaining traceability between the requirements and the systems is a key goal. The elucidation of the Logical architecture is explained in subsections 3.1. and 4.1..
- **Physical Architecture:** The physical architecture is modelled based on the placement of the actual systems that have been added to the semantics database, using the layout tool presented in Souflis-Rigas et al.,[29]. This tool is employed for the quantification of the impact of ambiguous regulatory statements.

- **Quantification of regulatory impact to design:** This layer refers to the Monte Carlo (MC) simulations conducted to sample the design space and gain a better understanding of the uncertainty by producing probability distributions for the KPIs of the design space.
- **Impact of Requirements:** In this layer, the different uncertainty scenarios are examined using comparative kernel density plots, scatter plots, box plots to analyze the characteristics of statements that lead to greater impact on the design space.

3.1. Interpretation of regulations to graphs using semantics

Regulations are interpreted using the ISO standard presented in Table 1. and illustrated in Figure 2.. The generated semantics database in Protégé, an open-source tool used to develop ontology databases [55], contains the information for the entities (i.e., systems) of the linguistic statement that can generate the dependencies of a graph and constraints for the physical architecture.

Table 1.: Comparison of ISO, Protégé, and Knowledge Graph Terminology for the semantic interpretation

ISO [56]	Protégé	Knowledge Graph [57]
Condition	Object, Object Properties	Nodes, Edges
Subject	Object	Nodes
Object	Object	Nodes
Constraint	Object Property	QoS
Value	Data Property	QoS, Medium

The semantic definitions used in this paper are the following:

- **“System”:** Systems $\Sigma^{(I)}$, $I = 1, \dots, n_I$ each have necessary input and output systems, as well as a medium representing the connection type. System components are added to the database, including their input and output interfacing systems and their specific medium (i.e., electric cable, fuel pipe, nitrogen pipe, etc.). For instance, the fuel pumps, electric motors, internal combustion engines, and batteries can be considered system components.
- **“Statement - Regulation”:** Requirements $R^{(I)}$, $I = 1, \dots, n_I$ denote the regulations that are used for our case study. They are the linguistic statements that describe the way that systems interact and are interpreted according to Figure 2..
- **“Constraints”:** As dictated in ISO, constraints have been integrated as object properties in the Protégé database to the type of connections that the systems are going to have. In Table 2., Regulations 4 and 6 indicate that systems should be mutually independent or separated, which states the need for distance between systems but does not clarify the distance required. Additionally, Regulation 3 sets the requirement for the sizing of the systems without clarifying the range in which systems need to be overdesigned for redundancy. Both cases underlie uncertainty and room for design space exploration to evaluate their impact.
- **Example of a statement interpretation to a graph:** Following the ISO standard described in Table 1., the statement presented in Figure 2. is interpreted as follows: the Subject is identified: “bunker station”, the Object: “fire fighting system” and the constraint “shall have” and the value “of alcohol resistant foam (ARAFFF-type)” which describes more specifically the functions expected out of the fire fighting system. The constraint indicates the dependency between the subject and the object. According to column *Knowledge Graph*, the Subject and Object are interpreted as nodes in the node graph, and the condition as the Edge that connects the two systems.

Figure 2.: Example of matching the statements of a regulation to the graph components that generates the topology

Based on the above, the semantic database proposed in this paper, denoted by \mathcal{F} , is implemented as:

$$\mathcal{F} = \mathcal{F}_s \cup \mathcal{F}_r \cup \mathcal{F}_c, \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{F}_s , \mathcal{F}_r , \mathcal{F}_c denote the set of “systems” statements by the designers, the “statements-regulations” by the stakeholders, and “constraints”. As can be seen in Figure 1., the first set is provided by the designer while the stakeholders shape the latter. The instances of \mathcal{F}_c are extracted from the regulations based on the condition interpretation and introduce uncertainty to the design space. Mathematically, this relation is expressed using the following mapping operation:

$$\mathcal{F}_r \times \mathcal{C} \mapsto \mathcal{F}_c, \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{C} denotes the set of conditions explained as part of the regulations.

3.2. Semantically Positioning Statements

To evaluate the statements, this paper proposes classifying them based on their perceived effect on the systems as a whole. The proposed classification aims to assess whether or not a statement can be classified as SMART [59] based on being “specific”, “measurable”, and “realistic”. This analysis does not examine the “traceable” and “appropriate” evaluations, as this adds another layer from the requirements to the needs and a mapping from the physical level back to the needs, complicating this initial study. These mappings are similar to the mapping from the requirements to the logical and physical architectures, adding unnecessary complexity. According to [4], the above goals can be translated into a need for the statements to be singular, complete, consistent, unambiguous, measurable, realistic, and feasible. The singularity of the statements is examined by the connections to the systems in Section 3.3.. The measurable, realistic, and feasibility aspects of a set of statements are evaluated in the case study in Section 4.. The feasibility part is verified by the execution or failure of the case study. The singularity of the statements is examined by the connections to the systems in Section 3.3..

To determine whether a statement fulfills these criteria via semantics, the statements are positioned in a two-dimensional axis system, depending on their “elasticity” and “hardness.” The distinction between the two axes aims to distinguish and visualize the impact of the two main protagonists in the requirements elucidation phase, the system and the stakeholders. On the one axis, “elasticity” denotes how the statements affect the boundaries of the design space. On the other axis, “hardness” denotes the persistence of stakeholders in modifying statements. This allows the stakeholders to identify possible high-impact statements or regulations and alter them if necessary. The actual impact of the statements on the design will verify the validity of the proposed positioning.

The classification of the statements on the “hard versus soft” axis denotes the notional room for change of the statement or regulation by the stakeholders (see Figure 3.). It also implies a priority ranking between the statements, allowing the stakeholders a visual aid in choosing which statements to alter, either by altering their wording or their actual meaning. It also functions as a measure of conformity and consistency. The conformity means that the statement conforms to the standard pattern presented in the Table 1., and the consistency means that the statements do not overlap and use homogeneous measuring units. The lack of

Table 2.: Analysis of the regulation statements key components according to ISO. [56]

ID	Reference	Regulation	Condition	Subject	Object	Constraint	Value
1	[58] Pt. 6 Ch.2 Sec 6 - 3.2.3.1	Fuel tanks shall be provided with an arrangement for inert gas purging and gas freeing.	<i>applies at all times</i>	fuel tanks	an arrangement for inert gas purging and gas freeing.	shall be provided with	NA
2	LR.Pt. 4 Ch.8 Sec. 2 - 6.1.1 a	When a distribution system is utilized to supply power to redundant consumers or systems, each consumer or system shall have a separate supply circuit.	When a distribution system is utilized to supply power to redundant consumers or systems	Each consumer or system	supply circuit	shall have a separate supply circuit	NA
3	LR.Pt. 4 Ch.1 Sec. 3 - 2.3.8	Active components, arranged as part of the designed redundancy, shall be so dimensioned that in the event of a single failure sufficient capacity remains to cover demands at the maximum continuous load of the component served.	In the event of a single failure	Active components, arranged as part of the designed redundancy	Dimensioning	Shall be so dimensioned	Sufficient capacity remains to cover demands at the maximum continuous load of the component served.
4	LR.Pt. 4 Ch.1 Sec. 3 - 2.3.9	When two or more components are performing the same function, these shall be mutually independent and at least one shall be independently driven.	When two or more components are performing the same function	Two or more components	Their operational independence and drive configuration	Shall be mutually independent and at least one shall be independently driven	NA
5	LR.Pt. 6 Ch.2 Sec 6 - 5.3.1.1	Fuel preparation rooms and engine rooms shall be protected by an approved fixed fire extinguishing system	<i>applies at all times</i>	Fuel preparation rooms and engine rooms	Approved fixed fire extinguishing system	Shall be protected by	NA
6	LR.Pt. 6 Ch.2 Sec 6 - 3.3.1.1	The fuel system shall be entirely separate from all other piping systems on board.	<i>applies at all times</i>	The fuel system	All other piping systems on board	Shall be entirely separate from	NA
7	BV.NR670 Ch.2 2.3.1	Direct access is not to be permitted from a non-hazardous area to a hazardous area.	<i>applies at all times</i>	access from a non-hazardous area to a hazardous area	direct access	not to be permitted	NA
8	BV.NR670 Ch.2 5.1.1	Inert gas should be available permanently on board in order to achieve at least one trip from port to port considering maximum consumption of fuel expected and maximum length of trip expected and to keep tanks inerted during two weeks in harbour with minimum port consumption.	Permanently on board	Inert gas	on-board availability of inert gas	should be available	In order to achieve at least one trip from port to port [...] minimum port consumption
9	NR547- Ch.2 21.1.	A fuel cell space containing fuel reformers is to comply with the requirements relevant for the primary fuel, especially considering the piping arrangements.	<i>applies at all times</i>	A fuel cell space containing fuel reformers	The requirements relevant for the primary fuel, especially considering the piping arrangements	is to comply with	NA
10	NR547- Ch.2 2.1.7	Boundaries between fuel cell spaces and other enclosed spaces are to be gastight.	<i>applies at all times</i>	Boundaries between fuel cell spaces and other enclosed spaces	NA	Are to be gastight	NA

these can create a requirement characterized as “soft”, as it is assumed that the statement is not final and there is room for change. Regarding the scaling of this axis, the conformity of the constraint is the main contributor. Specifically, the wording is compared to the standard wording of the requirements [4], which is “*condition, subject shall constraint, object, value*“. The keyword regarding the conformity here is “shall“, which is used for requirements. If “shall“ is not used, then the statement is not perceived as hard. The scale from hard to soft is the following: shall, need, is to, should.

The elasticity scale examines the room for interpretation of the statements. It investigates the “ambiguity“ and the “completeness“. The “completeness“ refers to the need for a statement to describe the necessary constraints and conditions sufficiently. This evaluation is boolean, dictating if a statement is positioned on the elastic or inelastic quadrants. In this case study, the “completeness“ is determined by the specificity of the “value” described in Table 1.. The ambiguity classifies the statements based on the clarity of their intent and the interpretation by all intended stakeholders in one or more ways. The ambiguity scaling is subjective, and the initial ranking was done by comparison of the statements, from the most ambiguous on the elastic quadrants and moving towards the inelastic when a specific object was defined, thus limiting the possible solutions.

None of the statements used were positioned in the “ambiguity” quadrant, as they reflect accuracy in language typical of classification society regulations. However, the regulations from DNV (regulations #7-10) did not use the appropriate wording, specifically the word “shall“. This led to the regulations being more aligned with stakeholder needs and goals. This does not mean that they are less important or inappropriate to be used, as the appropriateness of the statements is determined by the design phase in which they are encountered. According to INCOSE,[4], a SMART requirement, in the proposed positioning, should always be on the upper left quadrant. Yet, this does not take into account the process that creates these requirements. As per Kossiakoff et al.,[60], the requirements stem from stakeholder needs, which in turn stem from operational goals. Each of these terms is defined as the outcome of a concept design phase, the requirements elucidation phase, the needs analysis, and the initial identification of operational deficiencies. This then dictates a movement of the ideal positioning of the statements, starting from a soft and elastic goal, moving upwards to a harder stakeholder need, constraining the solution space slightly, and finally upwards and leftwards again to a hard, inelastic requirement. The trend is then established in the form of $y = -x$, where initially a more elastic and soft need is required moving leftwards and upwards to a more inelastic and hard requirement.

3.3. Interpretation of regulations to graphs using semantics

The process described in subsection 3.1. was applied to the regulations of Table 2.. By adding the corresponding connections between systems (i.e., power cable between electrical switchboard and fuel cell), the multilayer graph in Figure 4. is generated, which visualises the links between the regulations and the topology of the systems and helps keep track of regulations leading to potential design flaws.

- Layer Regulations: includes the regulations analyzed in Table 2. that are visualised as black circles.
- Layer Systems: includes the systems (red circles) that are the subjects or objects in the analyzed regulations. It also presents their topology in grey lines by adding the corresponding connections between systems (i.e., power cable between electrical switchboard and fuel cell).

The key takeaways in Figure 4. are the intralayer connections that can trace which regulations influence which systems. The intralayer connections are modelled as an undirected graph. In Figure 5., the degree centrality of the intralayer connections between the systems is calculated using Equation (3), which expresses the number of connections each regulations has [61]. Figure 5. shows that regulations #3, 4 are the most influential ones, followed by the equally influential regulations #1, 2, 6, 7, 9. The influence physically means that regulations 3 and 4 exert influence on the largest number of systems, dictating their positioning and size.

$$C_D(k) = \frac{\sum_{n=1}^N a_{nk}}{n-1} \quad (3)$$

Figure 3.: Qualitative regulations positioning on the hard vs soft-elastic vs inelastic axis. The numbers correspond to the regulations in Table 2.

where: $n = 1, \dots, N$ is the number of systems, k : expresses the node k and a_{ik} the values of the adjacency matrix.

Regarding the classification of the regulations as SMART, Figure 4. reveals no complete overlap, meaning having the exact same connections from the regulation to the systems layer, which verifies that they can be characterized as singular. As for the centrality, a high degree can be explained either by a regulation being highly influential to a large number of systems while being inelastic, for example, a safety regulation like regulation #4, or by an elastic and thus ambiguous regulation with numerous potential connections, like regulation #3. However, as it can be observed in Figure 5., in both cases, a high centrality degree requires a statement being hard, in addition to one of the conditions described above. Figure 4. shows via the dotted lines that regulation 4 affects the systems ICE, FC, and the electrical switchboards that are responsible for the power generation and link to the case study in Section 5.1..

4. Design Impact Quantification

4.1. Topology generation based semantic database

The logical architecture in Figure 6.a is produced according to the semantic interpretation presented in Kougiatsos et al.,[28]. The weights to the graph are assigned based on the piping type connecting two systems, as different piping requirements (e.g fuel piping, AC cables). The weights for the importance of these connections based on the medium have been extracted from [62], who performed a case study on a methanol engine room. A weighted adjacency matrix underlying 6.a serves as an input to the layout tool.

4.2. Integration with the layout tool

The layout tool that is used to quantify the impact of the regulations has been further elaborated on Souflis-Rigas et al.,[29] that is based on the implementation of the Facility Layout problem. The weighted

Figure 4.: Visualization of the multilayer network with Regulations and Systems layers.

Figure 5.: Degree centrality of the regulations to evaluate their impact.

adjacency matrix underlying the graph (see Figure 6.a) is a key component of the model as it quantifies the dependencies among systems, as this is an input to the layout tool. In previous work Souflis-Rigas et al.,[7] introduced an uncertainty evaluation framework for the engine room layouts that used MC to sample the corresponding design space. The generated layouts are optimized based on the connection costs between

the systems to generate layouts like in Figure 6.. Three KPIs are proposed to evaluate the impact of the different regulations:

- Length of the engine room: represents the impact on the overall size of the engine room, as it quantifies the length variation under uncertainty.
- Connection costs: quantify the sum of the weighted connection lengths between the systems and serve as the objective of the underlying optimization problem.
- Connection lengths: represent the actual calculated piping lengths that are necessary for the systems' connections. They indicate the necessary extent of piping within the engine room.

(a) Graph representing the system' logical architecture.

(b) Indicative layout of the case study systems configuration.

Figure 6.: Representation of the systems with their topology and physical architecture.

4.3. Analysis of engine room metrics to quantify design impact

The aim of this study is to better understand the relative impact of the regulation since the case study is focused on ESSD. The evaluation of the impact of these scenarios is conducted by visualising the outcome of the MC simulations with comparative figures:

- Comparative plot: visualises the relationships between the KPIs using the scatter plot that shows the relationships (see the lower left part of Fig. 7. the plotted points) and the curves for the probability density function for each KPI value (see the diagonal part of Fig. 7. the plotted points).
- Boxplot: is used to compare different case study scenarios and provide understanding for each KPI's central tendency, skewness, and outlier points (see Fig. 8.). The boxplots present all of the engine room size KPIs.

These visualisations provide an understanding of the relative influence of uncertainties for the different case studies and help identify which ill-defined aspects of the regulation may lead to a bigger impact.

5. Methanol vessel design case study

The classification of the regulations in Section 3.2. showed that there are aspects of regulations not clearly defined. This case study aims to quantify the impact of regulations #3 – 6 that are perceived as an

uncertainty source in Table 2.. The systems' dimensions that serve as inputs to the probabilistic layout tool are presented in Table 3. as well as the topology explained in Figure 6.a.

Uncertainty is generated by the “constraint part” in the regulations defined in Table (2.). Specifically, although a constraint is set, a clear value is not defined from the regulations for this constraint (marked as N/A in Table 2.). Three test cases were developed based on unclear regulation statements. Specifically:

- Subsection 5.1. presents the impact evaluation of uncertainty due to the requirement of sizing for additional redundancy.
- Subsection 5.2. evaluates the impact of safety constraints due to methanol integration, which do not clearly define the required distance between the systems.
- Subsection 5.3. explains the application of both uncertainties to the layout generator, with the focus being on the comparative evaluation of the regulations' impact.

Figure 7.: Comparison between different regulations: including scatter plots for the different KPIs and kernel density curves representing the probability distribution for each KPI of the problem.

5.1. Regulations specific to redundancy (#3)

Regulation #3, relative to the redundancy that is presented in subsection 3.2., the constraint statement of “shall be so dimensioned“ leads to uncertainty for the sizing and the dimensions of systems relating to power generation, as they do not define specific power requirements to size and dimension the systems related to

Figure 8.: Comparison of the perceived impact of regulations on the engine room KPIs.

Table 3.: Reference dimensions of methanol power and energy systems

System name	Width (m)	Length (m)
Electrical switchboard [1]	0.9	1.3
Electrical switchboard 2 [2]	0.9	1.3
Fuel cell [3]	0.9	1.2
Fuel tank [4]	1.0	2.0
Generator [5]	1.7	1.2
ICE [6]	1.7	3.5
Methanol fuel preparation [7]	1.8	3.0
Methanol reformer [8]	1.3	2.1
Nitrogen system [9]	0.5	0.5

power generation in the value section. The value part of the regulations lacks a formula to make a reliable estimation of acceptable sizing and dimensioning of the systems. Systems 1-6 were connected to Regulation 3 and therefore a 20 % uncertainty margin is applied in their dimensions. For the dimensions' uncertainty uniform distribution is used, as it assigns equal likelihood to all scenarios. Results in Figure 7. show a higher accumulation of points between lengths of 5.2 and 5.5 m. This happens because the layout algorithm can find similar positions for the systems; thus, no major repositioning is required. The connection costs and length distribution follow a distribution resembling normal. This is reasonable as connection costs are the objective of the optimization, and as such, they affect the generated solutions. There is an inconsistency between the probability distribution type of the input systems' dimensions and the distribution of KPIs serving as an output. This means that when the requirement for redundancy in the regulation is not clearly defined, the expected impact is inconsistent as well. This may lead to unforeseen design changes or failures. Additionally, Figure 8. shows that this scenario has many outlier points for the length metric (left boxplot) and uneven distribution. This indicates that specific combinations of systems' dimensions can lead to a design with a bigger overall size, as extra space is required for their layout arrangement.

5.2. Regulations specific to safe integration (#4, 5, 6)

The regulations that state the requirement for systems to be separated are the source of the uncertainty in this case study. These statements are found in regulations #4 - 6, where the constraint states that “*shall be separate*“. However no value is provided, which generates uncertainty for the required distance between the systems that need to conform with the regulation.

To quantify this uncertainty, a constraint is set for the longitudinal distance between the system pairs in Table 4. according to Equation 4. The required distance d_i introduces the uncertainty to the layout model. Although dimensions are kept fixed, it is clear that the distance constraint leads to a bigger impact for the

KPIs than the redundancy scenario (see Figure 8.). The distributions of the KPIs have a more irregular shape, and their values are visibly clustered. The length values have a higher probability density in 5.5 m and 6.4 m. The fact that the values of length and connection costs are more widely spread means that when specific distance constraints occur among the systems, they lead to a visibly bigger impact for the size and connections of the engine room (see Figures 8.). Connection costs and length have an irregular shape, but their value intervals remain with a few outlier points as illustrated in Figure 8..

$$\text{subject to: } |x_i - x_j| \geq d_i \quad (4)$$

Table 4.: Systems, distance, and corresponding regulations.

Systems	Selected distance uncertainty d[m]	Regulation
El. switchboard 1 - El. switchboard 2	1 - 2.5	Regulation 4
Fuel Tank - ICE	1 - 2.5	Regulation 6
El. switch. 1 - Methanol fuel preparation	1 - 2.5	Regulations 5, 6
El. switch. 2 - Methanol fuel preparation	1 - 2.5	Regulations 5, 6

5.3. Uncertainty contributed to both sets of regulations

In these scenarios, the safety and redundancy uncertainties are applied simultaneously to identify the scenario that affects the design space the most. Figures 7., 8. show that the distributions and the relationships of the KPIs under the different scenarios, with the combined scenario having an orange colour. Figures 7., 8. show that the safety regulation and the combination of the regulations have a high overlap in comparison to the redundancy regulations. Interestingly, the combination case can lead to a wider value range for all the engine room KPIs as visualised with Figure 8.. Although the safety regulations have a higher perceived impact, the occurrence of both regulation scenarios leads to greater uncertainty about the impact according to the box plot in Figure 8.. The impact does not add up linearly, meaning that the knowledge of the regulations' impact separately does not equal the combined impact. Figure 7. verifies this conclusion, as the green and orange points have extensive overlap regions both in the scatter plots and in the kernel density plots. In the context of this case study, the safety regulations have proven more influential on the design space than the requirement for redundancy. This is in accordance with the findings of [7] and highlights the need to further investigate and understand the impact of statements and systems dependencies on the design space.

This part of the study also addresses the “measurable” aspect of SMART. Specifically, the “measure” of a statement is determined by its impact on the design space. The uncertainty created by the statements examined in this case study resulted in significantly different KPIs, presented in Figure 7., which implies that the statements affected the design in various and distinct ways, thus they can all be classified as “measurable”. Regarding the relationship between the impact of the statement’s uncertainty with the positioning of the statements, the inelastic requirements for safety are more impactful than the equally “hard” but elastic redundancy requirement. As depicted in Figure 7., the design, when subjected to both requirements, appears to be driven by the inelastic safety requirements.

6. Discussion

Gaining a better understanding of the knowledge captured in linguistic statements is key to further advancing ship design both as a process and an end product. The semantic interpretation of functional requirements facilitates their translation into logical architecture of systems and design constraints, supporting a systematic approach to ship design. This marks a step towards the understanding of the interactions between different levels of systems architecture. Establishing the missing or ambiguous parts of the statements that dictate our design space can prevent failures from occurring when many design decisions have already been locked in.

The positioning of the statements in the “hard-soft, elastic-inelastic” axis can be used as a first estimate of the potential impact of a statement on the design and aid in evaluating the alignment with the SMART framework. Based on the initial positioning of the statements examined in this case study, the assumption of a trend in the form of $y = -x$ was detailed. This assumption was based on the need for harder and more inelastic statements as the design progresses to detailed design, as the need to constrain the design space is established. To validate these assumptions, the results of the case study were examined. The case study showed that the initial assumption that a statement on the upper left quadrant would be the most impactful was confirmed in Section 5.3.. Combining this with the examination of the degree of centrality of the produced multilayer network in Section 4.1., the conclusion that the impact of a statement is a function of its distance from the upper left corner of the axis system can be drawn. However, a correlation between the distance from the anti-diagonal and the statement affecting more systems is observed, and thus, for a statement to be “specific” in SMART terms, it needs to be positioned close to the aforementioned trendline. This enforces the assumption for the design phases optimal positioning on the anti-diagonal line.

Although Figure 4. traces the selected regulations to systems, not all of the dependencies or logical relationships among the systems can be traced back to the selected regulation. A source for them can be the operating principle among the systems (i.e. fuel flow from fuel preparation to ICE or electric power flow from FC to switchboard). The scope of this case study remains focused on regulatory analysis and the effort to perceive the impact of regulations both qualitatively and quantitatively.

7. Conclusion

This paper introduced a method for transitioning from written statements to the perceived impact of the properties, making statements ambiguous. The method allowed tracing requirements to systems to better understand the relationship of statements, leading to a perceived design impact. This was achieved with the designer’s semantic interpretation of the statements.

Regarding the semantic positioning of the statements in the hard vs elastic axis system, the assumptions revolving around the correlation of the positioning with the impact and the specificity led to the conclusion that they are functions of the distance from the uppermost left point and the anti-diagonal line, respectively. Furthermore, given that the different design phases require different types of statements as inputs, starting with operational goals, stakeholder needs, and requirements, it is concluded that the distance from the anti-diagonal is more crucial during the design process early on. However, when dealing with final requirements and regulations, both distances are equally important for a statement to be in line with the SMART framework. In conclusion, semantic positioning, in this context of ship design, provides a strong initial indication of the SMARTness and impact of a statement as validated by the methanol case study. However, analyzing further design requirements can be valuable in the future. Additionally, the designer remains a key part in the semantic interpretation of regulations regarding dependencies and constraints between systems. The ambiguous regulations were applied to a case study that modelled the layout of the systems in an engine room under uncertain scenarios linked to the regulations. The uncertainties in the regulations were identified to link with uncertainty in systems dimensioning and sizing (redundancy) and uncertainty in the distance constraint (safety) between systems. The case study found that the constraint to separate systems without clearly defining an acceptable distance for the separated systems influenced the design change in the engine room size more drastically than redundancy. Goal based standards that let designer select such parameters, can provide freedom to develop alternative designs.

The proposed framework in this paper provides a structured approach to quantify the relative impact of verbal statements to the 2D layout space, as shown in Section 5., as well as a validated approach to estimate the SMARTness and impact of a statement via the semantic positioning of the statement in terms of “hardness:” and “elasticity”, in Section 3.2..

7.1. Future work

Future work will focus on integrating operational and safety requirements in the proposed framework and exploring their impact on the vessel’s control systems design. Following this, the effect of interacting requirements on the design space can be of interest. Further automating the processing of statements and

keeping traceability to their impact in the actual design space is of value. This paper presented a first test case of the proposed framework and future research will expand the application to further regulations and design aspects affected by alternative power and energy systems configurations. Additionally, future work will include quantifying the interactions inside the systems architecture to expand the scope to the remaining layer of the RFLP, evaluate the effectiveness of the regulations, and create a traceability chain back to the stakeholders' requirements. Finally, it is worth mentioning that this analysis does not account for the operational needs of the stakeholders, which allows for the traceability aspect of the requirement elucidation process and the evaluation of the requirements' effectiveness. However, the methodology proposed in this paper can be expanded to account for this.

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